

8T – Discrete Curvature Ripples

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will argue that there is a beautiful way to explain the particle wave duality using the primorial and the setting of variational curvature. that is by analyzing Bosons as discrete curvature ripples which are diverging according to a variation of the Laplacian, it is also possible to correlate the curvature diverging time to the energy by inverse relation, which corresponds to the redshifts.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The wave equation of the Bosonic class is represented by the wave equation, which is net curvature diverging on the metric tensor. that is by a five-vector.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu\right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (3)_\mu\right) + N_{V\mu}$$

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V \quad (1.33)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial t_n^2} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2}$$

The key point to take from this is the following. It is possible to settle the issue of particle wave duality if we consider the idea of **discrete** ripples of net curvature. The discrete is manifested in the fact that the Bosons are isomorphic to the class of primes, and each Bosons has a unique signature of a prime. The Boson itself is represented by spin one-half, but as it is entangled with the majestic three, only than it accumulated as spin one. That is important if one would like to settle the subject of what is the light Quanta.

$$N_V = \prod_{\phi=1}^{\phi=N_V} \delta g_\phi = \delta g_{\phi=1} \times \delta g_{\phi=2} \times \delta g_{\phi=3} \dots \quad (1.23)$$

$$\delta g_{\phi=1} \equiv \delta g_{\phi=2} \equiv \delta g_{\phi=3} \dots$$

Therefore, the discrete nature is associative to the particle nature of the Bosonic class. In addition, the wave like nature is associative to the diverging nature of the ripple across the Lorentz manifold. It is possible to expend the idea using the spin representation as presented in the 8T thesis, in particular, it is possible to state the number of elements in the coupling term to a certain behavior, either particle or wave like. If the number of primes, including the majestic three is odd, than the overall behavior of the system would be particle like. If even it would be wave-like. Each prime added is considered a spin variant, which interfere with the overall system. As we can add prime together it means we can add those discrete ripples together to create the potentials itself, similar to summation of particles of a certain volume to get the potentials in classical field theories. Therefore, the light quanta is a discrete ripple of net curvature, prime isomorphic which diverge to all directions of the unique manifold, that is why the time is indexed in (1.33). The 8T framework is than allowing us to combine the nature of Quantum mechanics and discrete amount of energy, together with the setting of curvature and Riemannian geometry on continuous and smooth surfaces. It is also possible to correlate inverse relation between time and energy, and state that the longer the period of curvature diverging, the weaker the net curvature is, the more flat the ripple becomes. In physical theories that can correspond the redshifts.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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